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Shaping Engineering Education with the Power of Intelligent Internet of Things Technologies

Hsiao-Ping Tsai and Chih-Yu Wen

Department of Electrical Engineering
Graduate Institute of Communication Engineering
Innovation and Development Center of Sustainable Agriculture (IDCSA)
National Chung Hsing University
Taichung, Taiwan

ABSTRACT

With the developments of networked sensing and information processing technologies, significant breakthroughs have been made for the Internet of Things (IoT) applications. In order to successfully implement the IoT applications, smart and effective solutions linked to the cross-cutting issues will be an important subject in future engineering education. As we know, incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into the IoT already revolutionizes the world with the capabilities of improving operational efficiency and helping avoid unplanned system downtime. For instance, the IoT can capture large volumes of data in real time and this immediate feedback is important for adaptive learning systems. Data collected over time can also support AI to understand patterns, which can be useful for predictive analyses such as monitoring for potential future system failures and scheduling maintenance in advance.

Therefore, on the basis of our previous project (focusing on conducting project-oriented learning and using the application development training as a concrete embodiment of the interdisciplinary engineering education), the current project aims at achieving cultivation of creative thinking (Figure 2 (b)) and conducts two representative trainings: (A) Proposing AI-powered application proposals with IoT technologies and (B) Implementing the proposed projects with embedded systems, as depicted in Figure 3. Essentially there are four major steps involved in this one-year project: (1) Do: developing applications of Internet of Things (proposing a specific problem statement), (2) Check: performing capture, storage, and analysis of data (finding insights in data), (3) Adjust: executing data-based learning (validating and modifying the system design via AI-powered feedback), and (4) Plan: revealing insights that redefine the problem. On the topic of education training, we plan to arrange cross-presentation of creative thinking techniques and experience sharing in the field, which may allow the students to leverage AI-powered IoT technologies. This paper presents the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design process and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, internet of things, interdisciplinary engineering education.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the developments of networked sensing and information processing technologies, significant breakthroughs have been made for the Internet of Things (IoT) applications. In order to successfully implement the IoT applications, smart and effective solutions linked to the cross-cutting issues will be an important subject in future engineering education. As we know, incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into the IoT already revolutionizes the world with the capabilities of improving operational efficiency and helping avoid unplanned system downtime. As shown in Fig. 1, the IoT can capture large volumes of data in real time and this immediate feedback is important for adaptive learning systems. Data collected over time can also support AI to understand patterns, which can be useful for predictive analyses such as monitoring for potential future system failures and scheduling maintenance in advance.

For achieving cultivation of creative thinking and the realization of interdisciplinary engineering education, two representative trainings are conducted: (A) Proposing human-centric application proposals with IoT techniques and (B) Implementing the proposed projects with embedded systems. Referring to our previous project [1], essentially there are four major steps involved in this current project: (1) Integrating creative and design thinking with social care infrastructures and local services (e.g., visiting a nursing home, a special education school for the deaf, or a fire station), (2) Developing applications of Internet of Things (proposing a specific problem statement), (3) Embedded system implementations, and (4) Validating the system design via user feedback. On the topic of education training, we plan to arrange cross-presentation of creative thinking techniques and experience sharing in the field, which may allow the students to leverage IoT techniques and describe general issues of people-oriented problems through observation and discussion. This paper will present the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design process and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service.

Fig. 1. AI-powered IoT technologies [2].

2. AI-Powered Human-Centric Design Process

Our previous project explores the learning experience by integrating creative and design thinking with social care infrastructures and local services. Using the process

of design thinking presented by Stanford (Fig. 2 (left)), learners can translate their observations into insights, products and applications that can improve human life. Note that although the thinking process of is human-centred, it is a system design viewpoint. Furthermore, the industrial mentor may be consulted to guide the learners from discovering problems, defining issues, proposing possible solutions, and finally finding the best solution by using the Double-Diamond Thinking mode (Fig. 2 (right)). It is to be hoped that through the idea of the concept of creativity training, students can gain experience and skills for proposing general issues, which may provide a basis for defining specific problems (Empathy and Define). Then, through the combination of creative thinking training and engineering education, an appropriate solution may be explored to solve the problem (Ideate, Prototype, and Test).

Fig. 2. (a) Design thinking process [3] and (b) Double-diamond thinking model [4].

Therefore, on the basis of our previous project (focusing on conducting project-oriented learning and using the application development training as a concrete embodiment of the interdisciplinary engineering education), the current project aims at achieving cultivation of creative thinking (Fig. 1 (left)) and conducts two representative trainings: (A) Proposing AI-powered application proposals with IoT technologies and (B) Implementing the proposed projects with embedded systems, as depicted in Figure 3. Essentially there are four major steps involved in this one-year project: (1) Do: developing applications of Internet of Things (proposing a specific problem statement), (2) Check: performing capture, storage, and analysis of data (finding insights in data), (3) Adjust: executing data-based learning (validating and modifying the system design via AI-powered feedback), and (4) Plan: revealing insights that redefine the problem. On the topic of education training, we plan to arrange cross-presentation of creative thinking techniques and experience sharing in the field, which may allow the students to leverage AI-powered IoT technologies. This paper presents the preliminary results of this project, which emphasizes on human-centric design process and aims to develop an architecture model for problem solving and application service.

Fig. 3. Iterative process of AI-powered trainings [5].

2.1 AI-powered Application Proposals

On the theme of creativity and design thinking workshops, several lectures and experience-sharing group discussions will be arranged. Related Topics cover: the technology and concept of creativity and design thinking, training procedures, tools, and the need and importance of creative thinking in engineering education. Hope that through this workshop activities and thoughts training, students can cultivate the ability to think creatively in engineering education. For instance, guide students to think about the improvement of health-related quality of life and well-being (Fig. 4), considering sensing and recognition, knowledge processing, decision and support, and learning, which may lead the students to consider the design issue from cross-domain perspectives and may further provide a better solution for the caring of our society.

Fig. 4. Key procedures in the design of application tasks [6]

2.2 Intelligent System Implementations

Under the architecture of an IoT application as shown in Fig. 4, we detail on I/O interface, interrupts and control mechanism, process operation w/wo OS, and data flow and storage. In addition to setting up a development environment, students will conduct the labs on building a basic IoT device to sensing data, integrating multiple sensors and performing a complex sensing task, interacting IoT device with IoT gateway, processing data among IoT device, IoT gateway, and the sever end. Fig. 5 depicts possible scenarios of smart systems for achieving smart cities. To validate the system design, the users as well as domain experts are invited to give suggestions on the ideas and the proposals based on student’s demonstration, which provides an opportunity for students to review their idea and proposals. The suggestion of the users, the degree of accomplishment, and the discussion among the students are helpful feedbacks to revise the content of the program. Fig. 6 shows a non-linear process of validating the system design.

Fig. 5. Possible scenarios of smart systems [7].

DESIGN THINKING: A NON-LINEAR PROCESS

Fig. 6. A process of validating the system design [8]

3. Case Study

A course project may be applied to develop a practical application using IoT technologies. The students are grouped into teams to discuss application architectures from cross-disciplinary perspectives and propose their problem statements, project deliverables, system descriptions, project setups, prototype implementation, test and feedback. Accordingly, each team will deliver the full architecture of the system and the important pieces of implementation details. Here, we use an activity monitoring system as an example to describe the design issues of caring for an aging society. Possible healthcare scenarios for intelligent IoT applications are depicted in Fig. 7, where students may design a system from cross-disciplinary perspectives for environmental/safety monitoring. In this work, an AI-powered healthcare example, focusing on the conventional intravenous drip frame, is explored to demonstrate the project concept.

Fig. 7. Possible healthcare scenarios for intelligent IoT applications [9] (left); the balance control of the piggyback intravenous drip frame (right).

3.1 Problem Statement and the Design Goal

Due to the inconvenience of the conventional intravenous drip frame, the piggyback intravenous drip frame is developed to ensure better mobility of the patient. However, the current design of the piggyback intravenous drip frame leads to a lack of balance control and increment of blood returning. To this end, this invention applies proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control techniques and an inverted-pendulum system to build up a reliable system, which can facilitate patient mobility and ensure patient safety with compensating the inclination angle of the piggyback intravenous drip frame based on the motion information of the patient. Therefore, the reduction of blood returning and the balance control of the piggyback intravenous drip frame can be achieved.

3.2 Key Features and Contributions

Considering the conventional design of a drip frame, the fixed drip frame, including pulleys, is lack of the agility and convenience of movement. Although the new creative drip frame such as a shoulder-mounted (or mobile) drip frame (e.g., Taiwan Patent I522137 [10], M360702 [11]) has the mobility function, it can't adjust the position of the drip frame when user tilted forward, backward or other actions, which implies that the drip frame may tilt with user, reduce the height of the infusion tube, and increase the risk of blood return. Another kind of mobile design principle, such as portable intravenous drip pressurization injection device (e.g., Taiwan patent M368452 [12]), is to use additional gravity to drive drip output. However, the device is on the waist, which may be difficult to observe the remaining drip capacity. In order to overcome the above disadvantages, an innovative control strategy of the piggyback intravenous drip frame is proposed based on a motion sensor, a motor with PID control, and angle information, considering the effect of attitude determination and dynamic response performance of a piggyback intravenous drip frame. When the balance control activates, the gyroscope is used to get the acceleration, angular velocity and the tilt angle from the complementary filtering, which allows us to know whether the drip frame is tilted forward or backward (Fig.8 (bottom)). Compared with portable ringer's solution injection apparatus [13], the piggyback intravenous drip frame with balance control has the capability to control the drip frame for achieving the balanced state (perpendicular to the ground) during body tilting, the key features of this system are that the device

- can be moved with the human body,
- can cooperate with shoulder activities and neck activities,
- can correct the tilting angle of the body forward and automatically restore the angle.

That means the proposed system performs a control loop feedback scheme, conducted by a weighted sum of the control terms. Fig.8 shows a practical application with creative thinking and IoT technologies: the system prototype: a piggyback intravenous drip frame with balance control and the system workflow. The design of control system needs further improvement to make it more robust for different conditions in the future.

4. CONCLUSION

As shown in Fig. 9, 100+ Startups are currently transforming healthcare with AI. In this paper, an AI-powered IoT design concept is explored and a human-centric control system has been implemented for balancing a piggyback intravenous drip frame, which may provide an example to echo with the conference theme: "Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence."

Fig.8. A practical application with creative thinking and IoT technologies: the system prototype: a piggyback intravenous drip frame with balance control (top); System workflow (bottom);

Fig. 9. 100+ Startups in Healthcare with AI [14].

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